

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHER'S WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence works upon the philosophy that knowledge and skill may help someone get into the position, but it takes an emotional understanding of oneself and those around to emerge triumphant. Emotional intelligence influences the overall ability to cope with the environmental demands and uncertainties. When one understands the circuit of feelings, thoughts and reactions they can blossom into mature individuals. This helps in handling irrational fears, stressful situations, understanding strengths and overcoming weaknesses to cope up with challenges. Then the individuals can transcend self imposed limitations and actualize their potentials. They become adaptable, constructive, creative, productive and effective in their tasks. One cannot define emotional intelligence completely until one knows from where this concept originated and how it developed. The present study was conducted on 300 secondary school teachers from Medchal Malkajgiri district of Telangana State. The result reveals that there was a significant difference in emotional intelligence aspects with respect to gender among secondary school teacher's.

Key Words: Secondary Schools, Gender, Emotional Intelligence.

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Introduction

Emotional intelligence: Emotional intelligence (otherwise known as emotional quotient or EQ) is the ability to understand, use, and manage your own emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict. According to Daniel Goleman, an American psychologist who helped to popularize emotional intelligence, there are five key elements to it: Self-awareness, Self-regulation, Motivation, Empathy, Social skills. The last four decades of the 20th century

witnessed a dramatic change in the nature of work. There was a massive introduction of new technology, particularly the use of computers, into the workplace. This was followed by a huge shift towards globalization, with many organizations undergoing mergers, acquisitions, strategic alliances and privatizations. This entrepreneurial period resulted in increased economic competitiveness in international markets for those countries that embraced it. In the 1990s, a major restructuring of work started to take place. Organizations in countries hit by recession were downsizing in an effort to survive. With the dawn of the 21st century, this trend for restructuring and downsizing continued in many organizations, together with an increase in sub-contracting and outsourcing, in order to compete successfully in the increasingly competitive global market. A steady rise in short-term contracts, as a result, possibly, of the deregulation of long-term contracts and the limited requirements on permanent employment in many countries was witnessed. Other changes included new patterns of working, such as self-regulated work and team work, an increased reliance on computerized technology and a move towards a more flexible workforce, both in number of employees and in their skills and functions. In response to these adjustments by industry, the conditions of work and employment also changed significantly. The demand for skilled or multi-skilled workers increased in tandem with the growth of information technology and leaner, flexible manufacturing processes that required workers to multi – task. Supervisory conditions too changed with the introduction of teamwork, evaporation of the middle management, and the trends towards flexible place of “at – home” work arrangements. Also, the number of hours worked-per- week continued to increase for all occupations adding to mounting pressures and challenges. In other words we can say that transformation at workplace has set in, both in terms of nature of work and employees. The present day organizations take for granted that their employees have enough intellectual abilities and technical know-how to do their jobs. They are alongside laying emphasis on personal qualities, such as initiative, empathy, adaptability, persuasiveness, openness to change and willingness to diversify.

Objectives

1. To find the emotional intelligence among secondary school teacher’s in relation to their gender.

Hypothesis

1. There will be no significant difference between the emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers in relation to their gender.

Sample of the Study: The sample consisted of 300 secondary school teacher's from Medchal Malkajgiri district of Telangana State. India.

Tool of the Study

Emotional Intelligence Scale - Antara Dey and Nil Ratan Roy.

Five-fold Emotional Intelligence Scale for secondary school Teachers

This scale consists 28 items (2014).

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis – 1: There will be no significant difference between the emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers in relation to their gender.

Table 1: Showing Emotional intelligence Gender wise

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig.	Df
Emotional Intelligence	Male	150	21.41	2.71			
	Female	150	22.53	2.11	3.012	.05*	1,298
	Total	300	21.97	2.41			

From the above table, the mean score obtained for male teachers was 21.41 and female teachers was 22.53. The obtained t value 3.012 with a DF of 1,298 was found to be statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. It was clear from the above table that t Ratio for teachers with emotional intelligence came out to be 3.012, which was significant. Hence the hypothesis, which states that 'There will be no significant difference between the emotional intelligence among secondary school teachers in relation to their gender' is **rejected**. Majority of the secondary school teacher's had a difference in their opinions towards their emotional intelligence behavior with respect to gender.

Findings:

1. Gender: There was significant difference between the emotional intelligence among secondary school teacher's in relation to their gender.

Conclusion:

Emotional intelligence exists on a continuum and can be enhanced through positive relationships with supportive friends, congenial social opportunities, involvement in meaningful activities, and the effective management of stress and conflict. Schools can be key players in promoting the mental health, resilience, and overall healthy development of teacher's. The findings reveal that there was a significant difference in Emotional intelligence among secondary school teacher's with respect to their gender.

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